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DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF EDUCATIONAL SPACE

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Анотація. Освіта є одним із базових прав людини, закріпленим у 26 статті Декларації прав людини, Конституції України та Законі України «Про освіту». Якість та доступність освіти мають прямий вплив на доходи, зайнятість, розвиток, здоров'я та соціалізацію людей.

Війна посилила й розширила виклики, які вже постали перед освітою через епідемію COVID-19. Для української освітньої системи це випробовування стало ще й своєрідним стимулом, який відкрив вікно нових можливостей, ставши каталізатором давно назрілих модернізаційних змін в освіті. Передусім ідеться про розвиток цифрової та дистанційної освіти, зокрема онлайнової. Але перспективи трансформації освіти не обмежено лише цими напрямками. Потребують пильної уваги також розвиток неформальної та інформальної освіти, створення механізмів визнання її результатів у системі формальної освіти. На часі апробація та широке впровадження сучасних методів навчання з використанням інформаційних технологій.

Сьогодні, сама природа вищої освіти, як її набувають, і роль університетів в суспільстві та економіці змінюється і буде продовжувати істотно змінюватися в наступному десятилітті. Університети в усьому світі нещадно конкурують за студентів, науковців та фінанси, і в цю цифрову епоху виграють лише ті, хто зуміють залишитись відповідними часу та впровадять нові цифрові можливості.

Українське суспільство й нові інститути, що виникли внаслідок нагальної непередбачуваної трансформації життєвих процесів, – характеризуються стійкістю, адаптивністю, гнучкими підходами до формування і реалізації політики, культури, освіти, ведення бізнесу, розвитку територіальних громад, тощо. Українці стали «Learning Nation», – нацією, яка постійно вчиться та навчає інших завдяки динамічному розвитку системи освіти. Так вже склалося, що ми вчимося самі, пристосовуємося, змінюємося та змінюємо світ.

Варто усвідомити, що саме в наш час у глобальному інформаційному просторі відбувається зміна традиційних освітніх парадигм, форм організації освітнього процесу

та їх беззаперечна трансформація у цифровий формат. Зазначені тренди свідчать про перехід до цифрового суспільства. У таких умовах заклади вищої освіти мають перетворитися на технологічні центри, що відкривають нові можливості для всебічного розвитку особистості.

Ключові слова: цифрова освіта, заклади, модернізація, компетенції, інноваційна діяльність, гейміфікація, неформальна освіта, доповнена реальність, віртуальна реальність, дистанційна освіта, мобільні технології, хмарні технології, STEM-освіта, цифрове суспільство, кодування, програмування.

Annotation. Education is one of the basic human rights, enshrined in Article 26 of the Declaration of Human Rights, the Constitution of Ukraine and the Law of Ukraine «On Education». The quality and availability of education have a direct impact on people's incomes, employment, development, health and socialization.

The war has intensified and expanded the challenges already facing education due to the COVID-19 epidemic. For the Ukrainian educational system, this test became a kind of incentive that opened a window of new opportunities, becoming a catalyst for long-overdue modernization changes in education. First of all, it is about the development of digital and distance education, in particular online. But the prospects for the transformation of education are not limited only to these areas. The development of non-formal and informal education, the creation of mechanisms for recognizing its results in the formal education system also require close attention. It is time to test and widely implement modern teaching methods using information technologies.

Today, the very nature of higher education, how it is acquired, and the role of universities in society and the economy is changing and will continue to change significantly in the next decade. Universities around the world compete mercilessly for students, academics and funding, and in this digital age, only those who manage to stay relevant and implement new digital opportunities will win.

Ukrainian society and new institutions that arose as a result of the sudden, unpredictable transformation of life processes are characterized by stability, adaptability, flexible approaches to the formation and implementation of policy, culture, education, business, development of territorial communities, etc. Ukrainians have become a «Learning Nation», a nation that constantly learns and teaches others thanks to the dynamic development of the education system. It has already happened that we learn ourselves, adapt, change and change the world.

It is worth realizing that in our time, in the global information space, there is a change in traditional educational paradigms, forms of organization of the educational process and their undeniable transformation into a digital format. These trends indicate the transition to a digital society. In such conditions, institutions of higher education should turn into technological centers that open up new opportunities for the comprehensive development of the individual.

Keywords: digital education, institutions, modernization, competences, innovative activity, gamification, non-formal education, augmented reality, virtual reality, distance education, mobile technologies, cloud technologies, STEM-education, digital society, coding, programming.

Introduction

The requirements of the new times did not just speed up or contribute to the digitization of the educational process in all its aspects – they set an ultimatum to educators, which is aptly characterized by the term «urgent or emergency digitalization», which in turn marked a number of new requirements for the competencies and skills of educators.

The development of digital education initiates the emergence of new educational practices, which in turn contributes to the transformation of the educational system as a whole. The field of education, localized

by institutional, temporal and spatial frameworks, is significantly modernized due to the introduction of digital technologies into the educational process. Economic processes are actively changing, new types and forms of relationships are emerging in a unified information space, and, accordingly, new concepts and categories are emerging for understanding these processes, which were covered in detail in their research by such domestic and foreign scientists as: S. Evstrat'ev, L. Lyakhotska, H. Barjesteh, G. Blokdyk, H. K. Dhir, J. Garsdal, S. L. Gupta, U. Gupta, M. Heidarzadi, B. Heidkamp-Kergel, D. Ifenthaler, P. Isaias, A. Kaplan, D. Kergel, N. Kishor, M. Manoochehrzadeh, S. Mathur, N. Mishra, P. Ordóñez de Pablos, M. Paulsen, Y. Punie, C. Redecker, D. G. Sampso, and many others.

The purpose of this article is to study the main directions of transformational processes and radical changes in the national education system, to determine the digital competence of participants in the educational process, to characterize their dynamics and the irreversibility of the process.

Results

The large-scale invasion of Russia, which began on February 24, 2022, caused a complex of serious problems in Ukrainian education. First of all, this concerns the forced displacement of a significant number of the population of Ukraine and the destruction and damage of educational institutions as a result of military operations.

Over 10 million people changed their place of residence under the pressure of circumstances: 6.5 million within the country, 3.9 million went abroad. These are mostly women and children. UNICEF reports that more than half of the entire child population of Ukraine – 4.3 million children out of a total of 7.5 million – were forced to leave their homes. At the beginning of May, it was confirmed that more than 23,000 teaching staff and more than 600,000 students had gone abroad. However, these data are not final. Directors and rectors say that the whereabouts of about 10-15% of pupils and students have not been identified.

More than 1,748 educational institutions were affected by bombing and shelling, 144 of them were completely destroyed. 34 institutions of higher education (higher educational institutions – institutes, universities and academies), 42 institutions of professional pre-higher education (colleges) and 65 separate structural units moved. The number of war-affected and displaced higher education institutions grows every week.

Undoubtedly, the Russian armed aggression in 2022 led to significant changes in the higher education system of Ukraine as a whole. First of all, this is a reduction in state spending on higher education and budget places in higher education institutions, a decrease in population incomes, and a significant increase in «educational migration» can cause a significant decrease in demand for domestic higher education with corresponding consequences for teachers, administrations, and the network of higher education institutions. At the same time, the war rapidly accelerated the course of natural trends in the development of the higher education system regarding the optimization and correction of its structure, scope, and content.

Before the full-scale invasion of Russia on February 24, according to the State Statistics Service, 28.7 million people aged 14 to 70 lived in Ukraine (not including residents of the temporarily occupied regions of Donetsk and Luhansk regions and Crimea). Of them, 86% of people used the Internet, that is, 24.5 million Ukrainians were digitally connected.

But on February 24, a large part of Ukrainians moved to other regions of the country and abroad. In addition, part of our fellow citizens found themselves under occupation (fig. 1.).

Since we will talk about Internet trends later, it should be noted that ~19 million of them are the paying audience that uses the Internet (fig. 2.).

If we talk about global trends in Ukrainian digital until February, the level of Internet coverage in our country is at the level of other Eastern European countries – 86% (last year it was 82%), (fig. 3.).

Figure 1. Data of the State Statistics Committee of Ukraine on population movements in 2022
Source: Indicators calculated based on data from Digital Advertising Agency

Figure 2. Key factors affecting the digital audience of Ukraine, 2022
Source: Indicators calculated based on data from Digital Advertising Agency

Figure 3. The share of internet users in Ukraine among the population is at the level of other Eastern European countries
Source: Indicators calculated based on data from Digital Advertising Agency

Digital transformation of all spheres of human activity is a global world trend. In the last few years, it has been declared one of the leading areas of development in Ukraine. An important component of digital transformations in society is the so-called digitalization of education. It should be noted that this process is not simple and far from unambiguous. [3]

Digitization affects not only the content of education, but also its organization. These processes have mixed consequences for the positioning of the charter of both educational institutions and teaching staff. The necessary competences are most often acquired outside the walls of educational institutions, since educational programs, as a rule, do not keep up with the dynamics of technological development. The teacher from the bearer of knowledge and skills turns into a navigator who helps navigate new knowledge bases. Assessment of the content of scientific activity is replaced by formal details of science. The penetration of digital technologies into all spheres of life requires a new quality of education from the mass worker [5].

As early as 2020, radical changes in the organization of the educational environment have become quite a challenge for the domestic system of higher education. The transition to virtual networks from the space of educational classrooms, which happened suddenly and massively, intensified the practical implementation of issues that had been the subject of discussions among scientists until now.

The organization of independent work of students, effective interaction between teacher and student have become the main problems that require modern teaching methods and technologies. For teachers, the skills and abilities to methodically competently and technically optimally select the content of educational material, to be able to visualize the main parts of this content, to create cases for independent work of students, to organize interactive activities during the study of new material, to apply innovative methods that combine elements of mixed and distance learning have been updated etc. And in these conditions, competences in the field of independent learning, planning and self-development come first for students.

Therefore, digitalization appears as a key factor in improving the education system. In addition to the direct impact on the effectiveness of the educational process, digitalization provides a chain of indirect benefits. Thanks to digitalization, the educational process becomes more personalized, accessible and flexible [1].

Many universities have begun to develop their own digital strategies in response to significant changes in the use of new technologies, while lacking the vision, capacity or determination to implement them effectively. As a result, many institutions invested heavily in IT systems that did not provide the expected benefits and results. It's just that these institutions of higher education have not understood that what they really need is not a digital strategy – but a business strategy adapted to the digital age [9].

Staying relevant in the digital age requires a strategic vision across the institution, primarily from senior management with support from multiple departments, not just IT alone. The lack of digital literacy among teachers, scientists, students and staff requires early and deeper involvement to build an effective network of interaction. This, in turn, will become a necessary condition for achieving sustainable changes in the entire institution.

Higher education institutions that fail to adapt to this new digital age will be left behind. Whether a higher education institution wants to be a digital leader or simply stay relevant to the digital age, the time to act is now, even though «now» is too late.

Digitization is here, and it's here for the long haul. For example: today, always-connected mobile devices are everywhere; social networks are the main channel of communication for many people; the new capabilities of cloud computing enable the creation of new tools and products at a previously unimaginable speed; geolocation sensors create new possibilities for tracking and locating; digital media is the first choice of media today. The list can be continued. This leap is impacting and changing higher education and the academic community, and these changes will continue.

It is obvious that qualitative changes in the domestic educational space are impossible without global transformations and digitization – the introduction of modern digital technologies. However, digitalization is often perceived only from the perspective of a fashionable educational trend, being satisfied with its

superficial implementation, using it for the purpose of evaluating students' knowledge or visualizing educational material, the functionality of cloud technologies, digital data processing, and software [2].

In fact, digitization involves a fundamentally new format of the educational environment, based on digital technologies that provide convenient and accessible services and platforms for increasing competitiveness, more effective interaction of all participants in the educational process, increasing its transparency, increasing the role of intellectual property, and developing digital skills.

Students have now become customers who bring their own digital expectations of the world to the university. These customers are more savvy than their predecessors, better connected and more vocal than ever. Students increasingly consider universities to be the main means of securing their own future employment, and not just a place for learning and self-development.

Students, as a more digitally savvy generation, expect to learn in ways that are more suited to their personal preferences and at their own pace, rather than being forced upon them by traditional system-based learning.

This young audience is rapidly evolving, embracing new tools and applications at a pace that even the most active institutions of higher education are struggling to keep up with. And as competition from trusted substitutes for higher education, such as colleges, advanced courses, and more, continues to grow, higher education institutions must demonstrate that they can provide the digital experiences that students now take for granted [3].

In today's digital age, where the voice of the education consumer is more critical than ever, turning students into advertisers and advocates for higher education is one of the most powerful marketing tools.

The modern world is filled with absolutely new opportunities for obtaining an education. More and more institutions of secondary, technical and higher education offer online courses, trainings and webinars. This, of course, also has its advantages, because training takes place in a convenient place, at a convenient time. Some alternatives are becoming more popular, such as home schooling or different approaches aimed at development without the use of books and a strict system of control. Such work stimulates creative activity, therefore, students begin to feel free in their work and can ask any questions about the discipline [8].

The main resource of digital education is information. Digitization of education is already changing the traditional system of education in the direction of forming its new quality. This is manifested in the following:

- ✓ the number of virtual educational platforms is increasing;
- ✓ one electronic resource can be used many times to provide educational services of different content;
- ✓ introduction of new technologies in education and digital educational platforms that provide services.

Determinants determining the quality development of innovative digital education are: establishment of horizontal and vertical connections between faculties, universities, enterprises, investors; creation of a national educational platform; intra-university mobilization of personnel; new technologies of motivation for participation and formation of digital and innovative skills; updating the educational program in the direction of its digitization; interest in the innovative culture of the university, its projects; the development of digital culture and the spread of the spirit of innovative activity; mutually enriching exchange between universities and faculties; young personnel in the field of education, which is ready for changes as a result of digitalization of the country's economy.

Another important «inhibitor» of using digital resources in institutions of higher education is digital literacy. This should be understood as knowledge, skills and confidence in using available technologies and devices to achieve the desired results. Therefore, universities face a real large-scale task of covering processes with digital technologies, especially the learning process [6].

It is appropriate to remember that it is also necessary to form the digital literacy of both the modern student and the digital competences of the teachers of the higher school. Digital education today is more than

digital literacy. The importance of digital tools in the real life of children and adults is constantly increasing, and digital media literacy is a key characteristic of the 21st century.

To succeed in today's innovative economy, a person must possess new competencies – constantly updated, even compared to the recent past. The formation of the knowledge economy and globalization processes affect the structure of the labor market, increasing the dependence of successful employment and effective professional activity of a person on the accumulated human capital, the most important role in the formation of which is played by the level and quality of education.

There is an urgent need to develop digital competencies, to master the latest information and communication technologies for pupils, students, and teaching staff, which will contribute to the development of critical thinking, the ability to make independent reasoned judgments, and the ability to learn throughout life.

The use of information and communication technologies opens up new opportunities for the design and implementation of the educational process, and requires the assimilation and development of digital competencies. Information and communication technologies, in particular, make education more accessible, diversify the forms of obtaining it, ensure the continuity of education throughout life, the development of personally oriented education, etc.

The main trend in modern education is the introduction of the «lifelong education» model, which enables a person to adapt and develop his competences and professional skills in accordance with rapid changes in the economy, technology and labor markets. This model contains the following subsystems:

- informal education (according to the degree of institutionalization);
- distance education (according to the method of organizing the educational process);
- online education (by means of implementation);
- mixed education (combination of traditional and online means of education).

Distance learning, online learning, and blended learning are undeniably closely related. Distance and online learning technologies are used in blended learning. Online learning is used in distance learning, but it can also be done asynchronously. The concept of continuous learning, which appeared in the late 20th and early 21st centuries, is based on the need for lifelong learning in the modern technological world [5].

Informal education is also a trend of modern education, which is now an important component of continuous education, in particular in connection with the accelerated aging of knowledge. Informal education is the acquisition of new knowledge about various aspects of life through training through various courses, interest groups, master classes, etc. In the framework of non-formal education, as a rule, no prerequisites are required for starting education (preliminary training, age limits, etc.), there are no strict requirements for the place, time, terms, forms and methods of education, which allows a much larger number of people to be included in the learning process, than in formal education [7].

The most developed types of online education in Ukraine are distance and blended learning. Under during the pandemic and then during martial law, they provide opportunities to organize the educational process.

There are several more popular educational trends among consumers of educational services, which can be conditionally divided into the following blocks (fig. 4.):

Programming or coding. Today it is perhaps the greatest and most in-demand skill of the 21st century. This is because in the digital society, computer programs are at the heart of business, marketing, aviation, science, medicine and many other industries. That is why basic programming skills are now needed for various professions, as already now more than 90% of professionals need digital competencies, a large part of which is related to the ability to program. The ability to program is an important component of the digital literacy of a person living in a digital society [6].

STEM. This is a direction in education, under the conditions of its use in educational programs, the natural and scientific component is strengthened with the use of innovative technologies. The development of STEM fields in education is of crucial importance for the development of modern society, since STEM

education is the basis for training specialists in the field of high technologies. STEM education is based on the use of tools and equipment related to technical modeling, energy, electrical engineering, informatics, information technologies, scientific research in the field of energy-saving technologies, automation, robotics, intelligent systems, radio engineering, radio electronics, aviation, cosmonautics, aerospace technologies etc. STEM education is the foundation for science education [7].

Figure 4. The main trends of digital education in 2022

Source: Figure reproduced based on the authors' own research

Cloud technologies. This concept refers to technologies of distributed data processing, using which computer resources and capacities are provided to the user as an Internet service. The main directions of using cloud technologies in education are cloud services for educational institutions; cloud platforms for training, testing, etc.; cloud data storage.

Gamification. It is the use of game practices and mechanisms in a non-game context to engage users in problem solving. The basis of the gamification strategy is the reward for completed tasks, which includes various types of incentives (points, awards, levels, progress indicators, virtual currency, etc.). An important element of gamification is competition, which allows you to stimulate participants to complete tasks by encouraging other participants with awards, bonuses, etc.

Virtual reality. This is a world created with the use of technical means, which can be perceived by a person through the senses: sight, hearing, smell, touch, etc. In fact, it is a three-dimensional computer model of a physical environment in which the user can move and interact with the objects of this environment.

Augmented reality. Modern technology of interactive computer visualization, which allows you to supplement the image of the real world with virtual elements and display it on the device screen. With the help of this technology, the perception of virtual images in the real world is formed in users, and not by creating an alternative world.

Mixed reality. This is an environment created with reference to the real world. In mixed reality, virtual elements are added to a person's usual environment, which are attached to their place in space so that the observer perceives them as real.

Technologies of virtual, augmented and mixed reality contain enormous potential for solving the main tasks of the educational process. Their use affects all components of students' cognitive activity.

Mobile technologies in education are used in such main areas as mobile learning and the use of mobile devices as an auxiliary tool in the educational process. Usually, mobile learning is understood as the use of mobile technologies both separately (for example, a distance learning system for mobile devices) and together with other information and communication technologies to organize the educational process regardless of place and time.

One of the most common ways of using mobile technologies in education is the principle of BYOD (Bring Your Own Devices). It is related to the use of smartphones, tablets, netbooks and other digital devices for educational activities. Under this condition, pupils (students) use their own devices, that is, the devices are not provided by the educational institution.

A valuable resource for the modernization of the educational system, especially in the context of the problems caused by the war, is the development of non-formal education. The Law of Ukraine «On Education» has already laid the foundations for the development of non-formal education and the recognition of its results – now an important task is to legislatively define the specific mechanisms of this process. Article 9 of the same Law defines, among other forms of education, distance, online and external education. They can be implemented as efficiently as possible only under the condition of a high level of digitization of the educational process, for which three directions must be developed: organizational-legislative, methodical and infrastructural. Only their combination can achieve the desired effect [10].

An important direction of digitization of education is the widespread introduction of high-quality electronic textbooks into the educational process. However, today they are simply PDF versions of paper books. This format does not cover the multimedia capabilities of digital information transmission (interactivity, dynamic iconography, video content, etc.).

In addition, there is a significant demand in the modern labor market, especially in middle and senior positions, for so-called soft skills (flexible skills), which do not refer to purely professional competencies, but are a complex of super-professional non-specialized skills – responsibility, time management, ability to work in a team, leadership and social influence skills, emotional intelligence, flexibility, adaptability, etc [6].

In order for the triad to work – education, scientific research, implementation of innovations – the higher school must interact with high-tech production.

Nowadays, when the war against Ukraine is going on, the cooperation of domestic scientists and enterprises of the defense complex is extremely important. In the conditions of external aggression, the military-political leadership of the state needs high-quality scientific and analytical, predictive studies. Ensuring the creation of such developments, primarily in the interests of Ukraine's national security, should be taken into a separate direction of scientific and technological development [10].

Accomplishing such a task requires joint efforts and constant coordination of scientists and representatives of the defense and security sector. Accordingly, there is a need for a single point of effort and knowledge, a single scientific center capable of uniting scientists from various institutions and ensuring constant coordination with state bodies that determine the state's security policy.

Education is the best tool available for innovation. However, he also has a problem. In order to achieve exclusive innovations, education must radically change.

To be valuable, education must primarily teach teamwork, curiosity, and problem-solving skills. As artificial intelligence and automation take over jobs, the education of tomorrow must strengthen our competitive advantage over machines. It is here that you should pay attention to two human strengths that are difficult for digital technologies to reproduce: creativity and empathy. The education system should be built on this [9].

Creativity is the source of all innovation. It allows humans to adapt over the centuries and create art in all forms that machines cannot achieve. This makes it an added value that cannot be compared with computers.

Empathy is the ability to relate to others, to develop solutions that take into account a wide range of emotions, to create a unique context. This skill also cannot be codified and is the key to a successful career.

There are many things that the education system can do to encourage people to develop these skills and improve them throughout their lives.

Not so long ago, lifelong learning became an everyday and widespread practice. A critical mass of individuals and communities aimed at occupying new professional niches has been formed.

A radically updated education system plays an important role in supporting the Learning Nation ecosystem. It includes:

- an open national educational platform with services for the formation of individual educational trajectories;
- integration of formal and informal education system;
- transformation of economic complexes of classic educational institutions into educational innovation hubs;
- culture of lifelong learning.

Conclusion

Digital education is education that functions primarily through digital technologies, that is, electronic transactions that are implemented through the use of the Internet. The 21st century is a time of great transformations, the formation of an information society, accelerated innovation and network connections, so the question of the imperative of forming digital education in Ukraine is objective.

The events of recent years have brought unprecedented corrections to educational activities in the world in general and in Ukraine in particular, making online education not only necessary, but also in some cases the only possible way to ensure the continuity of the educational process, the implementation of educational programs and the access of pupils and students not only to educational materials, but also to learning as such.

The impossibility of conducting education in the classical way in classrooms at desks presented educators with an unprecedented challenge: to find a meaningful way to continue education online. The sudden need for digital solutions in the field of education led to the emergence of various digital networks and online platforms, the role of which in ensuring the educational process is currently difficult to overestimate [4].

For digitization to be successful, education institutions must first invest in providing staff, researchers and students with the necessary digital training and connect them with effective support networks. Workers and academics should be given the freedom and flexibility to try out innovative ways of working with digital technologies, without fear of criticism or punishment.

In order to implement digital literacy among scientists, teachers, employees and students, it is necessary to start expert groups for providing support for digital technologies. Innovative workers pushing the boundaries of what is possible with digital technology should be encouraged to join these support groups so that they can act as catalysts for change and feel that their efforts are valued and encouraged.

There is no one-size-fits-all way to achieve concrete results in improving educational services through digital technologies, but listening to end users can provide valuable insights and adapt them to the demands of modern life.

Perspective directions of further research. It should be noted that the implementation of digital technologies is very important for the development of the system of higher and professional education, but along with this, it is necessary to form a scientifically based approach to their implementation. A promising education system should be able not only to arm the student with knowledge, but also, as a result of the constant and rapid updating of knowledge in our era, to form the need for continuous independent mastery of knowledge, abilities and skills of self-education, as well as independent and creative activities throughout the entire active life a person

The authors' prospects for further research include the development and implementation of innovative educational technologies, modules and gadgets related to the use of world experience. After all, the

information and educational environment is a current trend that provides unique opportunities for all, without exception, participants in the educational process.

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